

ANALYTICAL MODELLING OF STRESS-STRAIN CURVES FOR FIBRE METAL LAMINATES

M. Hagenbeek, J. Sinke and C.G. van Hengel

Faculty of Aerospace Engineering

Delft University of Technology, P.O. Box 5058, 2600 GB Delft, The Netherlands

e-mail: M.Hagenbeek@lr.tudelft.nl

ABSTRACT

In the search for optimal performance, metals and fibre-reinforced epoxy are combined to obtain 'the best of both worlds'. An example is Glare, Glass reinforced aluminium, a fibre metal laminate which consists of aluminium layers and glass fibre layers embedded in epoxy adhesive. The number and thickness of the aluminium layers may vary, and also the number of prepreg layers and their orientation. The stress-strain curve for the laminate turned out to be a combined fibre-metal chart, which depends on the fibre orientation and the loading direction. Methods to describe stress-strain curves for aluminium have been studied extensively. However, the combination of aluminium and glass-prepreg in Glare gives a stress-strain curve which is more complex to describe. Plasticity of the aluminium and residual stresses after curing, due to the difference in thermal expansion of the constituents, must be taken into account.

A tool has been developed to calculate the uniaxial stress-strain curve for an arbitrary fibre metal laminate. The tool is called SSCP, Stress-Strain Calculation Program, and includes plasticity, internal stresses after curing and the effect of prestraining. The stress-strain curve is assumed to be bilinear and the Bauschinger effect as well as reversed plasticity is taken into account in the prestrain modelling. The method provides an easy and fairly accurate determination of the (laminate) stress-strain curves of fibre metal laminates.

Key words: Stress-strain curves, Bauschinger effect, fibre metal laminates, residual stresses

Figure 1 Uniaxial stress-strain curve for Glare 3-3/2-0.3 without prestrain and in aluminium rolling direction (L). Maximum laminate strain limit is 4.5% due to the fibres.

INTRODUCTION

For the next generation of aircraft newly developed materials like the fibre metal laminate Glare offer great advance in fatigue resistance, residual strength and weight reduction. Five different Glare configurations have been designed with two aluminium alloys and specific fibre lay-up, see Table 1 (Roebroeks 1997). Combinations of materials are made to obtain the ‘best of both worlds’. In the case of Glare the glass fibres increase the residual strength and improve the fatigue performance, whereas the aluminium adds plasticity, which increases the (impact) damage tolerance and formability and reduces the stress concentration. These newly built laminates consist of more than one material and are anisotropic. By changing the lay-up, the laminate can be tailored to obtain optimal advantage of the diverse properties. The stiffness of Glare depends on the lay-up and fibre orientation. The effect of the tailoring on the stress-strain curve can easily be investigated once an analytical model has been developed. A calculation method for *uniaxial* stress-strain curves of Glare has been developed by Horst, Ohrloff and Bär (1993), who have used the semi-empirical Ramberg-Osgood relation to describe the elasto-plastic behaviour of the aluminium. A more general approach to calculate an *uniaxial* stress-strain curve of an *arbitrary* fibre metal laminate is presented in this paper.

Table 1 Material composition of Glare laminates.

material grade	metal layers		fiber layers	
	alloy type	thickness [mm]	fiber orientation	thickness [mm]
GLARE 1	7475-T761	0.3-0.4	0/0	0.250
GLARE 2	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	0/0	0.250
GLARE 3	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	0/90	0.250
GLARE 4	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	0/90/0	0.375
GLARE 5	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	0/90/90/0	0.500

Source: Roebroeks 1997

Elastic and plastic part

The stress-strain curve for aluminium, and more general, for metals, consists of an elastic part and a plastic part. For pure aluminium the plastic part of the stress-strain curve rises only very slowly. This could be approximated by a perfectly plastic model. After yielding no further increase of stress is necessary to produce plastic strains. In most engineering materials, such as mild steel and all alloys, an increasing stress is required for continued plastic deformation; this effect is called *strain hardening*. After unloading only the elastic strain is recovered, but permanent plastic deformation has occurred. After the ultimate stress is reached, most metals still yield and finally fail at a somewhat lower engineering stress level. For many alloys the stress-strain curve can be approximated by a bilinear curve with reasonable accuracy. The stress-strain curve for (glass-) fibres is usually linear elastic up to a maximum strain level.

A calculation tool for *uniaxial* stress-strain curves, based on bilinear behaviour up to a maximum strain level, has been developed. For each arbitrary laminate composition (e.g. aluminium, steel, titanium, carbon fibre, glass fibre) and for each different loading direction a specific stress-strain curve will be found.

THE UNIAXIAL STRESS-STRAIN CURVE PROGRAM (SSCP)

The developed tool calculates the stress-strain curve for an arbitrary Glare lay-up (Figure 1) and applied prestrain (Figure 4). The tool calculates the *residual stresses* after curing, accounts for *plasticity* of the aluminium and allows the user to apply a *prestrain* to the laminate. The curing temperature is assumed to be the stress-free condition of the laminate (Gürdal, Haftka, and Hajela 1998). In the elastic and plastic region the stiffness of the aluminium is assumed to be constant. In compression the same elastic modulus as in tension is used, the plastic stiffness is different.

Residual stresses after curing

After curing residual stresses remain in the laminate due to cooling down and the different coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the glass-fibres and the aluminium. Since the CTE of aluminium is the largest one, the aluminium layers are loaded in tension; the fibres in compression after the curing process. This effect is unfavourable in fatigue loading, since the residual stresses add to the mechanical stresses. To obtain better fatigue performance and higher yield stress levels prestraining can be applied to the material in order to reverse the residual stress system.

In addition to temperature-related expansions, composite materials expand by absorbing moisture from the environment. This effect is small in Glare material, since the fibre layers are shielded by the aluminium layers. In the present paper the effect is not taken into account.

Plasticity

Three different types of material behaviour are generally possible; linear elastic, linear elastic up to the yield point and ideal plastic after yield; linear elastic up to yield and strain hardening (or softening) after yield (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 Three different types of material behaviour.

Usually a linear part is found in the strain hardening part of the stress-strain curve. The linear elastic and linear plastic line part of the curve intersect at point K, see Figure 2c, if both parts are extended. In this way, an idealised bilinear curve is obtained.

Figure 3 Stress-strain curves during unloading and reloading paths (Besseling and van der Giessen 1993)

In the calculation tool for the aluminium both the elastic and plastic, strain-hardening, part are assumed to be linear. Up to the yield point an elastic E-modulus is used and beyond the yield point a plastic E-modulus.

Prestraining

By means of prestraining the internal stress distribution can be reversed. The laminate is mechanically loaded beyond the aluminium yield point. After reloading yielding occurs at a higher stress level, see Figure 3.

When the material is reloaded (after unloading) plasticity restarts not exactly at the previously attained stress (σ_B), but somewhat before that level (at point D), and upon further deformation the curve approaches

the stress-strain curve that would have been found if the loading had not been interrupted (dashed curve B-F in Figure 3). Similarly, if the unloading path BB' is continued by further compression, yielding will occur before the compressive stress has reached the value σ_B (that would have been reached in case of isotropic hardening without prestraining). This is interpreted as a reduction of the elastic stress limit or flow stress in absolute value due to the previous strain hardening, and is known as the *Bauschinger* effect (Besseling and van der Giessen 1993).

The elastic regime at this stage stretches between $-\sigma_E$ and σ_B , and is no longer symmetric relative to the unstressed situation. For all engineering materials, the size of the elastic regime, $\sigma_E + \sigma_B$, appears to be bounded as follows:

$$2 \cdot \sigma_Y < \sigma_E + \sigma_B < 2 \cdot \sigma_B \quad (1)$$

and it depends on the material and on the current strain level which of the two bounds is closest.

The previous observations pertain to tests performed up to strain levels of about 5% (Besseling and van der Giessen 1993).

The Bauschinger effect is accounted for in the prestrain modelling of the curve. The total elastic stretch in the reversed curve is roughly of the order of twice the elastic stretch in the initial loading curve. Consequently, the elastic strain limit in absolute value has been diminished by the previous strain hardening.

The effect of 2.5% prestrain on the stress-strain curve of Glare 3-3/2-0.3, which consists of four aluminium layers of 0.3 mm thickness and three prepreg layers, is shown in Figure 4. The general lay-up of this Glare configuration can be found in Table 1 (Roebroeks 1997).

Figure 4 Uniaxial stress-strain curve for Glare 3-3/2-0.3 with 2.5% prestrain (continuous line) and without prestrain (dashed line). The loading is in the aluminium rolling direction (L). Maximum laminate strain limit is 4.5% due to the fibres.

FORMULATION OF THE SSCP TOOL

Elastic and plastic part

In the elastic region a rule of mixtures is used to calculate the Young's modulus of the laminate E_L :

$$E_L \cdot t_L = E_{Al} \cdot t_{Al} + E_{0^\circ} \cdot t_{0^\circ} + E_{90^\circ} \cdot t_{90^\circ} \quad (2)$$

The thickness of each constituent, t_{Al} , t_{0° , t_{90° , is the total thickness of all layers of the same constituent. t_L is the total laminate thickness and further the Young's modulus E of each aluminium and 0° and 90° glass-fibre layer is filled in.

If plasticity is taken into account the Young's modulus of the laminate is calculated in a similar way. The yield strength of the laminate σ_{yL} is derived with;

$$\sigma_{yL} = E_L \cdot \sigma_{yAl} / E_{Al} + ((E_{Al} \cdot \sigma_{rAl} - E_{Al} \cdot \sigma_{rAl}) \cdot t_{Al} + (E_{Al} \cdot \sigma_{r0^\circ} - E_{0^\circ} \cdot \sigma_{rAl}) \cdot t_{0^\circ} + (E_{Al} \cdot \sigma_{r90^\circ} - E_{90^\circ} \cdot \sigma_{rAl}) \cdot t_{90^\circ}) / E_{Al} \cdot t_L \quad (3)$$

by taking the contribution of each layer to the residual stresses σ_r into account.

Residual stresses

The residual stresses can be determined with the thermal expansion coefficients α and the operating and curing temperature, T_o and T_c respectively with the following formula:

$$\sigma_{rX} = (E_{Al} \cdot t_{Al}(\alpha_{Al} - \alpha_X) + E_{0^\circ} \cdot t_{0^\circ}(\alpha_{0^\circ} - \alpha_X) + E_{90^\circ} \cdot t_{90^\circ}(\alpha_{90^\circ} - \alpha_X)) \cdot E_X \cdot (T_r - T_c) / (E_L \cdot t_L) \quad (4)$$

where X denotes either the desired property for aluminium, 0° fibre layer or 90° fibre layer. The ultimate stresses in each layer are calculated by adding the stress after curing, yield stress and the stress increment from yield to final failure.

In Table 2 the coefficients of thermal expansion α_1 , in 0° direction, and α_2 , in 90° direction of the glass fibre-epoxy and the isotropic α of the aluminium are listed. All CTE's are values at an operating temperature T_o of 20°C . The coefficients of thermal expansion for the total laminate and the corresponding residual stresses are listed in the same table for a Glare 3-3/2-0.3 laminate. The coefficient of thermal expansion for the total laminate α_L , in 0° direction, can be determined with:

$$\alpha_L \cdot t_L = \alpha_{Al} \cdot t_{Al} + \alpha_{0^\circ} \cdot t_{0^\circ} + \alpha_{90^\circ} \cdot t_{90^\circ} \quad (5)$$

where α_{Al} , α_{0° , and α_{90° are the coefficients of thermal expansion for aluminium and glass fibre-epoxy in 0° direction and 90° direction. To calculate the coefficient of thermal expansion for the total laminate in 90° direction α_{0° , and α_{90° are interchanged. The coefficient of thermal expansion for aluminium α_{Al} is the same in all directions since aluminium is isotropic.

Table 2 Coefficients of thermal expansion for glass fibre-epoxy and aluminium and residual stresses determined with the Stress-strain Calculation Program for Glare 3-3/2-0.3 constituents.

Glare 3-3/2-0.3	α [$^\circ\text{C}$]	σ_r [MPa]
Aluminium	23.4×10^{-6}	19.9
Glass/Epoxy 0°	$6.15 \times 10^{-6} (\alpha_1)$	-70.5
Glass/Epoxy 90°	$26.2 \times 10^{-6} (\alpha_2)$	3.3
Laminate 0°	$20.7 \times 10^{-6} (\alpha_1)$	-
Laminate 90°	$20.7 \times 10^{-6} (\alpha_2)$	-

Source: SLI, 1995

Prestraining

The internal stress system in the laminate can be altered by prestraining the material. For example to improve the yield strength of a Glare laminate, which has an unfavourable tensile stress in the aluminium layers after curing.

The stress-strain curve without prestraining can be constructed by calculating the stress and strain at four points; zero stress in the aluminium, zero laminate strain, aluminium yield stress, and ultimate strain. The compressive part follows from the tensile part, where it is assumed that the Young's

modulus is the same both in compression and tension $E_{Al,c} = E_{Al,t} = E_{Al}$. The compressive yield strain can be determined as:

$$\varepsilon_{y,c} = \sigma_{y,c} / E_{Al,c} - \sigma_{r,Al} / E_{Al,t} = (\sigma_{y,c} - \sigma_{r,Al}) / E_{Al} \quad (6)$$

The calculated laminate stress and the internal stress distribution for each strain can easily be verified by checking the force equilibrium:

$$\sigma_{Al} \cdot t_{Al} + \sigma_{0^0} \cdot t_{0^0} + \sigma_{90^0} \cdot t_{90^0} - \sigma_L \cdot t_L = 0 \quad (7)$$

The stress-strain curve after prestraining is calculated in several steps. First the stress distribution due to the prestrain is calculated both for the new tensile and compression yield point of the curve. The tensile yield point lies at the prestrain value, the initial compression yield point is shifted with the same amount as the tensile yield point:

$$\varepsilon_{y,c,p} = \varepsilon_{y,c} + (\varepsilon_p - \varepsilon_{y,t}) \quad (8)$$

where $\varepsilon_{y,c,p}$ and ε_p are the compression and tensile prestrain and $\varepsilon_{y,c}$ and $\varepsilon_{y,t}$ the initial yield strain without the prestraining effect respectively. The second step is to calculate the residual stresses after prestraining when the laminate is unloaded again. Since the laminate stress should be zero at this point the residual strain ε_r is calculated as follows:

$$\varepsilon_r = \varepsilon_p - \sigma_{L,p} / E_L \quad (9)$$

with $\sigma_{L,p}$ as the laminate stress due to prestraining. Once the residual strain is known the residual stresses in the layers can be calculated as:

$$\sigma_{X,r} = \sigma_{X,p} - E_X \cdot (\varepsilon_p - \varepsilon_r) \quad (10)$$

where the X denotes either the desired property for aluminium, 0° fibre layer or 90° fibre layer. However, in case the prestrain is very large, expressions (9) and (10) do not hold any more. During unloading the aluminium will start yielding before the laminate has reached the zero stress level. This so called *reversed plasticity* is taken into account and the residual stresses are corrected as follows:

$$\sigma_{X,c,r} = \sigma_{X,p} - E_X \cdot (\varepsilon_p - \varepsilon_{c,r}) \quad (11)$$

$$\sigma_{Al,c,r} = \sigma_{Al,c,p} - E_{Al} \cdot (\varepsilon_{c,p} - \varepsilon_{c,r}) \quad (12)$$

where the corrected residual strain $\varepsilon_{c,r}$ is calculated with

$$\varepsilon_{c,r} = \varepsilon_{y,c,p} - \sigma_{L,c,p} / E_{L,p} \quad (13)$$

with the before mentioned formula's the stress strain curve for an arbitrary Glare laminate can be determined with the effect of residual stresses after curing, plasticity and prestraining effects including the reversed plasticity and the Bauschinger effect, see Figure 4.

The yield stress at 0.2% strain

All formula's before mentioned the laminate and aluminium yield stress to be at the knee point of the stress-strain curve. However, in general a 0.2% offset strain value is used to determine the yield point. Beyond this point remaining plasticity is found in the material. For aluminium 2024-T3 the stress value at the knee point and at 0.2% offset strain is small as the Young's modulus in the plastic region has a very small value. For the Glare laminate the Young's modulus in the plastic region is still substantial and the 0.2% offset yield stress will thus be considerably higher.

The ultimate strain

The ultimate strain of the laminate is assumed to be 4.5%. The failure strain criterion is derived from the fibres, the aluminium fails at much larger values (10.8% in the test, see Table 3). The 4.5% failure strain is correct for all laminates except for Glare 2 tested in the LT-direction perpendicular to the fibres.

COMPARISON OF CALCULATION AND EXPERIMENTS

The results of the calculated yield and ultimate points for several Glare laminates are compared in Table 5 with the published values (Roebroeks 1997), based primarily on testing. The material composition for the tested Glare laminates is given in Table 1 and the used material properties for the aluminium and the glass-fibre epoxy prepreg are found in Table 3.

The deviation of the calculation with respect to the published values is between -2 and 5 % for the ultimate tensile strength. The deviation for the tensile and compression yield is larger, see Table 5.

In Table 4 the calculated and experimental coefficients of thermal expansion, published by Roebroeks (1997), are shown for two different Glare 2 and Glare 3 lay-ups. The agreement between calculation and experiment is well.

The calculated stress-strain curves of Glare 2-3/2-0.3, Glare 3-3/2-0.3, and Glare 4A-3/2-0.3 are also compared with experimental curves in the longitudinal direction (L), i.e. the aluminium rolling direction, and the transverse direction (LT) of the laminate. The calculations are in agreement with the experimental results, see Figures 5, 6 and 7. The difference in ultimate strength between calculation and experiment in L and LT direction is respectively -4 % and 6 % for Glare 2-3/2-0.3, 0 % and -1 % for Glare 3-3/2-0.3, 0 % and 6 % for Glare 4A-3/2-0.3.

Figure 5 Comparison of the calculated and experimental stress-strain curve for Glare 2-3/2-0.3 in the longitudinal direction (L), and the transverse direction (LT).

Figure 6 Comparison of the calculated and experimental stress-strain curve for Glare 3-3/2-0.3 in the longitudinal direction (L), and the transverse direction (LT).

Figure 7 Comparison of the calculated and experimental stress-strain curve for Glare 4A-3/2-0.3 in the longitudinal direction (L), and the transverse direction (LT).

Table 3 Material properties of the Glare constituents in compression (c) and tension (t) used in the SSCP program. Note that the denoted yield strength values (σ_{y-c} and σ_{y-t}) are in fact the determined knee points.

Material	Direction [°]	Elastic E [Mpa]	Plastic E _c [Mpa]	Plastic E _t [Mpa]	σ_{y-c} [Mpa]	σ_{y-t} [Mpa]	α [1/K]
Aluminium	0	73085	1401	887	-296	357	2.34E-05
	90	73085	1048	1228	-331	310	2.34E-05
Prepreg	0	48500	48500	48500	-	-	6.15E-06
	90	6000	6000	6000	-	-	2.62E-05

Table 4 Calculated and published (based on testing, Roebroeks 1997) coefficients of thermal expansion of Glare laminates.

Material grade	Lay-up	CTE published [x10 ⁻⁶ /°C]		CTE calculated [x10 ⁻⁶ /°C]		Difference	
		α_1	α_2	α_1	α_2	[%]	[%]
Glare 2	2/1-0.3	18.5	23.7	18.3	24.2	-1%	2%
	3/2-0.3	17.2	24.6	17.2	24.4	0%	-1%
Glare 3	2/1-0.3	20.8	19.0	20.6	20.6	-1%	8%
	3/2-0.3	20.5	20.3	20.8	20.8	1%	2%

Table 5 Comparison of calculated and published (based on testing, Roebroeks 1997) Glare laminate properties.

	(2)	Published GLARE (1)				Calculated GLARE (1)				Difference [%]			
		2	3	4	5	2	3	4	5	2	3	4	5
		Tensile ultimate strength [MPa]	L	1074	717	930	682	1059	705	937	685	-1	-2
	LT	317	700	592	673	327	685	622	664	3	-2	5	-1
Tensile yield strength [MPa]	L	360	305	352	296	334	285	290	289	-7	-7	-18	-2
	LT	228	283	255	280	211	250	218	253	-7	-12	-15	-10
Tensile modulus [GPa]	L	65	58	57	59	64	56	55	57	-2	-3	-4	-3
	LT	50	58	50	59	48	56	48	57	-4	-3	-4	-3
Ultimate strain [%]	L	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5				
	LT	10.8	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5				
Compression yield strength [MPa]	L	415	310	365		344	270	297	271	-17	-13	-19	
	LT	236	310	285		224	296	256	298	-5	-5	-10	
Compression modulus [GPa]	L	67	59	60	59	64	56	55	57	-5	-5	-9	-3
	LT	52	59	54	59	48	56	48	57	-7	-5	-11	-3

(1) GLARE 1 to 4: 3/2 lay-up with 0.3 mm aluminum
 GLARE 5: 2/1 lay-up with 0.5 mm aluminum
 (3/2 lay-up: 3 layers aluminum, 2 layers fibers)

(2) The L-direction is the aluminium rolling direction.
 The LT-direction is perpendicular to the aluminium rolling direction.

CONCLUSIONS

- The calculation tool for uniaxial stress-strain curves is an easy and effective method to calculate the stress-strain curve for an arbitrary (Glare) laminate and allows a fast, preliminary investigation of the effect of plasticity and prestraining. The method only needs data for the constituents and extensive testing of each different laminate and lay-up is not necessary. The method gives fairly accurate predictions.

FUTURE WORK

- At this stage, the yield and ultimate stress values for the metal part of the laminate are used together with the internal stresses to obtain the stress-strain curve (in 0°, 90° or 45° direction). In the future a stepwise calculation method will be followed for the stresses in each individual layer until yield or fracture of a certain layer is reached. After yield or fracture has occurred, the calculation is advanced with a new defined plastic or zero stiffness for that particular layer.
- The prestraining effect on the biaxial stress-strain curve will be implemented in the extension of the current program.
- The calculation of the stresses around holes or damages will allow a prediction of the fatigue crack initiation, which is a future objective.

REFERENCES

- [1] Besseling, prof. J.F. and Giessen, prof. E. van der; *“Mathematical Modelling of Inelastic Deformation”*, Engineering Mechanics & Continuum Mechanics and New Materials, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands, 1993.
- [2] Gürdal, Z., Haftka, T. and Hajela, P.; *“Design and Optimization of Laminated Composite Materials”*, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, University of Florida, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, 1998.
- [3] Horst, P., Ohrloff, N. and Bär, H.; *“The influence of pre-stretching and temperature on the static and damage tolerance behaviour of GLARE material”*, Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM/9), Madrid, 12-16 July, 1993.
- [4] Ramberg, W. and Osgood, W.R.; *“Description of stress-strain curves by three parameters”*, NACA TN-902, July 1943.
- [5] Roebroeks, G.H.J.J.; *“GLARE, a structural material for fire resistant aircraft fuselages”*, AGARD Conference Proceedings 587, Paper presented at the Propulsion and Energetics Panel (PEP) 88th Symposium on “Aircraft Fire Safety”, held in Dresden, Germany, 14-17 October 1996, published in CP-587, September 1997.
- [6] SLI, *“Customer data information sheet”*, 1995.